

EFFECT OF REPRODUCTION IN UNICORNUATE UTERUS WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

Background: Unicornuate uterus is an uncommon condition which is an inherited anomaly of the mullerian duct with notable reproductive, gynaecologic, and obstetric outcome. In general complications are linked to presence or absence of a rudimentary horn, mostly when it comprises a functional endometrial cavity. Knowing the pregnancy outcome and reproductive performance in unicornuate uterus women is important for optimising clinical care of the women's reproduction and pregnancy outcome. **Methods:** This systematic review gathers the findings from nine primary studies and case reports to evaluate reproductive outcomes, clinical presentations, diagnostic modes, and obstetric complications in unicornuate uterus women. This systematic review examines trends in risks, imaging techniques which were related to functional rudimentary horns, and analyses the different strategies for the management of the condition to give combined evidence based out line. **Results:** A functional

rudimentary horn was an essential decision for complications like the rupture of the uterus, severe and chronic pelvic pain, ectopic pregnancies, and endometriosis in most of the studies that are reviewed. Reproductive function: live birth rates were between 38% and 61%, miscarriage rates between 16% and 42%, obstetric complications like preterm birth rates between 17% and 21%, fatal malfunction rates between 18% and 48%, C-section rates higher than 60%, and twin pregnancies having a lot of risks. And the ectopic pregnancy risk was also high, especially for those women with a functional rudimentary horn. Accuracy in diagnosis should be improved with advanced transvaginal ultrasound and MRI(Magnetic resonance

imaging) scans. The following systematic review collected evidence upholding the prophylactic excision of a functional rudimentary horn, which may prevent further rupture and reduce conditions like endometriosis. **Conclusion:** Women with a unicornuate uterus are susceptible to various forms of reproductive and obstetric difficulties, mostly if a functional rudimentary horn is existing. personalized management techniques should be individualized, putting focus on preconception counselling, early pregnancy surveillance, and multidisciplinary high-risk obstetric care. Prophylactic removal of functional horns may improve the outcome by lowering life-threatening complications.

KEYWORDS: Unicornuate uterus, Rudimentary horn, Müllerian anomaly.

INTRODUCTION

The unicornuate uterus is an uncommon condition that is an inherited anomaly of the Mullerian duct that causes a hemi uterine structure frequently followed by a rudimentary horn.^[2, 5, 9] And its incidence rate is low in major cohort studies.^[4,7,9] This anomaly carries significant reproductive, obstetric, and gynaecological departments.^[3,7,8,9] The presence, type, and functions of a rudimentary horn are the important considerations, and other considerations include fertility potential and complications.^[1,2,7,9] The women with unicornuate uterus present with dysmenorrhea, chronic pelvic pain, recurrent pregnancy loss, infertility, or even with no specific symptoms.^[1,4,9] 3 Dimension transvaginal ultrasound and MRI scans are used for diagnosis.^[4,7] A functional rudimentary horn is related to increased risk of thoracic and pelvic endometriosis, retrograde menstruation, and life-threatening rudimentary horn pregnancy.^[1,7,9] Several studies show the reproductive performance and outcome are affected by increasing preterm delivery, miscarriages, and ectopic pregnancies.^[3,5,7,9] Despite these risks, most of the women with a unicornuate uterus attain successful live pregnancies.^[3,6,9] Unicornuate uterus is considered a high-risk gynaecology and obstetrics condition that needs close pregnancy monitoring.^[3,7,8]

METHODS

Search Strategy and Study Selection

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systemic Reviews and Meta Analysis) 2020 guidelines to evaluate the reproductive outcomes, obstetric performance and other related complications in patients with a unicornuate uterus. An extensive search was conducted in electronic databases such as PubMed, and Google scholar. The search utilized keywords such as "unicornuate uterus,

"rudimentary horn," "Müllerian anomaly," "ectopic pregnancy," "preterm delivery," and "in combination with Boolean operators (AND, OR) to maximize the retrieval of relevant literature. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs), cohort studies, case-control studies, and case reports that reported fertility outcome, pregnancy complications, surgical management or perinatal performance in women with unicornuate uterus were considered for inclusion criteria to represent the evaluation of diagnostic imaging and current clinical understanding. Articles between March 1987 and March 2025 were considered for the review in order to reflect the most recent advancements in the field.

Study Inclusion and Screening Process

Three reviewers screened titles and abstracts separately for relevance. Full texts of potentially relevant articles were screened against predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria aimed at the contribution of the effect of reproduction in unicornuate women. The process of selection is represented in a PRISMA flowchart Figure.

Data extraction

Questionnaires are used to extract important and essential information from studies that are included. Which includes, study design and population, methods used for assessment and results. The data which is presented in table 1.

Quality Assessment

For determining methodological rigor and reliability of the findings, quality appraisal was conducted using Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) critical appraisal tools relevant to the research design.

JBI Checklist for Cohort Studies

JBI Checklist for Case series

JBI Checklist for Case Reports

Three reviewers independently assessed all studies. Discrepancies were addressed by discussion. Studies that met high or moderate quality standards with the appropriate JBI tool were included in the synthesis only to guide sound conclusions.

Figure 1: The Study selection process based on the PRISMA guidelines 2020.

TABLES

Name and year	Country	Study design	Sample size	Study population	Age range/ mean age	calculation	Groups
Case reports							
Matalliotakis I.M. 2002	Greece and USA	Case report	1	29-year-old woman with catamenial haemoptysis, secondary infertility, stage iii pelvic endometriosis, unicornuate uterus with a non-communicating rudimentary horn	29 years	Not used calculation method	Single patient
Handa Y. et al., 1999	Japan	Case report	1	18 years old primigravida woman with tubal pregnancy in a unicornuate uterus with a non-communicating rudimentary horn	18 years	Not used calculation method	Single patient
Case series							
Fedele et al., 1987	Italy	Retrospective and prospective observational studies	21 women initially, but 19 women including in analysis (2 excluded due to being 14 and 15 years of age)	Women diagnosed with unicornuate uterus, confirmed by hysterosalpingography and laparoscopy	Not explicitly stated in the article	Unicornuate uterus was based on Buttram and gibbons' classification with four sub classes (A1a, A1b, A2, B) % abortions, % premature labour, % term delivery	4 groups
Cohort							
Name and year	Country	Study Design	Sample Size	Study Population	Age Range/mean age	Calculation	Groups
Lin wang et.al 2024	China	Retrospective cohort study	Unicornuate uterus group :94 Nulliparous women control	Nulliparous women with singleton pregnancies; diagnosed with unicornuate uterus after 28 weeks of gestation	Mean maternal age :29.29 ± 3.22 years	Students t-test, Mann-Whitney U chi-square/F Isher, Multivariate	Unicornuete uterus group (n=94) Control group

			group :278 women (Total evaluate d for outcomes = 372			binomial logistics regression (adjusted for age ,BMI, gravidity, Mode of conception)	with normal uterus morphology (n=278)
T. Tellum et al. 2023	UK	Single -centre retrospective cohort study	326 women with unicornuate uterus, with 326 matched controls	Women aged 16 years or older diagnosed with unicornuate uterus by transvaginal /transrectal ultrasound between 2008 and 2021	Participants aged 16 years and above mean age 34 ± 9.5 years	Primary outcome: live- birth rate, secondary outcome: miscarriage (early &late), ectopic pregnancy, preterm delivery, mode of delivery, and gynaecological combabilities	Study group- women with unicornuate uterus control group -women with normal uterus matched 1.1 by age and BMI
D Mavrelou et al 2007	UK	Prospective observational diagnostic study	8 cases of “cornual pregnancy”	Women with suspected pregnancy in a rudimentary horn of a unicornuate uterus undergoing ultrasound in a tertiary referral centre	Not specified	Pre -defined ultrasound criteria and confirmed by operative +histological findings	Non communicating horn pregnancies
Moutos et al., 1992	US	Retrospective comparative cohort study	54 women (29 unicornuate +25 Didelphic)	Women diagnosed with unicornuate or didelphic uterus receiving care in gynaecology and reproductive endocrinology services	Unicornuate uterus group -28.4 years, didelphic uterus group -20.4 years	Wilcoxon’s rank sum test, two-tailed t-test, chi-square test, and life table analysis	Unicornuate group and Didelphic uterus group
Si wang et al 2025	China	Retrospective cohort study	283 women with a unicornuate uterus included 21 twin pregnancies (Group A) 262 singleton pregnancies (Group B) 105 twin pregnancies with normal uterus as control (Group C)	A comparison control group of twins -pregnant women with normal uterus	23-36 years	SPSS version 22.0; chi-square test, fishers exact test, independent sample t-test, Mann -Whitney U test; statistical significance set at p<0.05	Group A -twin -pregnant women with unicornuate uterus (n =21) Group B – singleton-pregnant women with unicornuate uterus (n =262) Group C -twin-pregnant women with normal uterus (control group) (n=105)
Pentti K. Heinonen — 1997	Finland	Retrospective cohort study	42	Diagnosed with unicornuate uterus (with or without rudimentary horn)	15 -79 years (mean age 28)	Laparotomy, plus hysterosalpingogrophy	Unicornuate uterus with rudimentary horn containing cavity unicornuate uterus with rudimentary horn without cavity unicornuate with no rudimentary horn

Table 1: Data extraction from the collected studies.

Name and year	Follow-up duration	Limitations	Assessment methods	Key findings
Case reports				
Matalliotakis I.M. 2002	3years	Single case report, so it's difficult to generate results Unclear treatment which has the treatment like (pregnancy hormonal state, GnRH therapy, or surgical removal of rudimentary horn) which led to full remission	MRI was done during menstruation presenting right-sided pulmonary consolidation Bronchoscopy (negative) Diagnostic laparoscopy identifies and confirms stage III pelvic uterine anomaly and endometriosis	Patient had pulmonary endometriosis which is also associated with unicornuate uterus and noncommunicating rudimentary horn GnRH agonist that is (leuprolide acetate) effectively suppressed haemoptysis and menstruation Symptoms get after menses but again resolved with therapy Pregnancy occurs to the women after therapy; surgical excision of rudimentary horn resulted in permanent resolution
Handa Y. et al., 1999	8 months after salpingectomy, laparoscopic resection of rudimentary horn was performed Indicates 8-month follow-up	Single case report, so it's difficult to generate results No fertility is observed after removal of horn	Ultrasonography Emergency laparotomy, Pathological microscopic examination MRI Hysterosalpingography (HSG)	tubal pregnancy occurring on the same side as a noncommunicating rudimentary horn with an ipsilateral corpus luteum The rudimentary horn had no endometrial cavity, that making tubal pregnancy difficult because the fertilized ovum could not enter the uterus Pregnancy occurred likely due to transperitoneal migration of sperm/ovum Post-surgical removal of rudimentary horn that improve reproductive outcomes and prevent future complications
Case series				
Fedele et al., 1987	2 to 10 years	Small sample size (19 women) Retrospective reproductive history evaluation no standardized obstetric management for unicornuate uterus	Diagnosis confirmed by laparoscopy and laparotomy Hysterosalpingography used for classification of unicornuate uterus Intravenous urography in 16 patients for renal anomalies	31.6% of women never conceived Total live birth rate: 38% (8 term births out of 29 pregnancies) 58.6% abortions, 10.3% premature births

		Results not apply to all subtypes of uterine anomalies because of heterogeneity		Pregnancy in rudimentary horn: 3.4% 81.8% caesarean deliveries Removal of rudimentary horn improved reproductive outcomes in some cases
Cohort				
Lin wang et.al 2024	90 months (prospective observational study)	Prospective diagnosis using pre- and well-defined transvaginal ultrasound criteria: (1) single interstitial portion of fallopian tube in main uterine body; (2) gestational sac mobile and separate from the uterus, surrounded by myometrium; (3) vascular pedicle joining sac to the unicornuate uterus. Final outcomes confirmed by operative findings and histology when surgery was performed; clinical follow-up for conservatively managed cases.	Very small sample size (8 cases). Single tertiary referral centre (limits generalisability). Observational design — no control group or comparative diagnostic test accuracy statistics. Variable management approaches between patients (heterogeneous treatments).	Eight cases of cornual (rudimentary horn) pregnancy were diagnosed over the 90-month period. When the ultrasound criteria were met, the diagnosis was subsequently confirmed at surgery and on histology in the surgically managed cases — indicating the described ultrasound features are reliable markers for this rare ectopic pregnancy location. Management varied by viability and gestational age; one woman managed expectantly had recurrence later.
D Mavrelos et al 2007	Retrospective review of pregnancies recorded from March 2009 to March 2019 (10 years). No postpartum follow-up duration specified.	Retrospective study design. Relatively small sample size. Control group not randomly selected — potential selection and confounding bias. Limited data to evaluate risk of uterine rupture during labor.	Diagnosis and evaluation based on: Transvaginal ultrasonography (TVS) Hysterosalpingography Hysteroscopy and/or laparoscopy Obstetric and neonatal outcomes collected from hospital records.	Unicornuate uterus significantly increases risks of preterm delivery, PROM, PPROM, malpresentation, caesarean section, IUGR, and NICU admission. Lower gestational age at delivery and lower rate of vaginal delivery compared to normal uterus. Vaginal delivery is possible and safe after careful evaluation — unicornuate uterus is not an absolute indication for caesarean section.
Moutos et al., 1992	Mean follow-up duration: 7.0 ± 5.9 years (unicornuate group) and 10.1 ± 7.7 years (didelphic group)	Included only women who already presented with reproductive/gynaecological issues → may not represent all women with these anomalies Insufficient sample size to assess role of uterine anlage	Review of medical records from 1950–1990 Diagnosis via: laparotomy/laparoscopy, hysteroscopy, HSG, MRI Follow-up via record review, referring physicians, or	Reproductive performance of unicornuate vs. didelphic uterus showed no significant difference Most women with either anomaly eventually achieved a live birth

		No comparison to general healthy population regarding miscarriage/preterm risk	telephone contact	Spontaneous abortion and preterm delivery rates appear increased, but routine cervical cerclage is not supported without cervical incompetence Caesarean section and breech presentation rates were higher than the general population
T. Tellum et al. 2023	Covers ultrasound-diagnosed patients from January 2008 – September 2021 (13-year retrospective follow-up window)	Some demographic / clinical details unavailable (e.g., age at each pregnancy, indication for surgery) Population may not represent general public (based on patients attending a gynaecology clinic)	Transvaginal / transrectal ultrasound with 2D & 3D imaging used to diagnose and classify unicornuate uterus Comparison with age- and BMI-matched control group with normal uterine anatomy Pregnancy outcomes assessed: live birth, miscarriage, ectopic pregnancy, preterm delivery, mode of delivery, and gynaecological abnormalities	Lower live-birth rate in women with unicornuate uterus (47.4% vs. 57.8% in controls) Higher risk of adverse outcomes, including: Miscarriage (a OR 2.21) Ectopic pregnancy (a OR 2.52) Preterm delivery (aOR 3.04) Caesarean delivery (aOR 2.54)
Si wang et al 2025	The study is retrospective over 10 years (January 2013 – December 2022) — follow-up is through perinatal period until delivery and neonatal discharge.	Retrospective design Single-centre study Limited sample size due to rarity of twin pregnancies with unicornuate uterus Need for larger multicentre prospective studies for validation	Retrospective cohort analysis Review of medical records of women delivered at West China Second University Hospital Comparison of 3 groups: Twin pregnancies with unicornuate uterus Singleton pregnancies with unicornuate uterus Twin pregnancies with normal uterus Statistical tests: Chi-square, Fisher's exact test, Mann-Whitney U test, independent sample t-test using SPSS 22.0	Twin pregnancies with unicornuate uterus had markedly increased perinatal risk. Significantly higher rates of: Preterm delivery (85.7%) PPROM (38.1%) PROM (42.9%) NICU admissions (64.3%) Lower neonatal birth weight (mean 1931.7 g) Higher haemorrhage at delivery 90.5% required caesarean delivery. Overall pregnancy and neonatal outcomes are good when pregnancies are closely monitored.
Pentti K. Heinonen — 1997	Mean follow-up 9 years (range: 3 months to 25 years)	Study design was retrospective Sample size limited to 42 cases over 33 years Some patients lacked complete renal evaluation (only 34 tested)	Retrospective study Laparotomy/laparoscopy for diagnosis Hysterosalpingography or hysteroscopy	Most common anomaly: right unicornuate uterus with non-communicating rudimentary horn High ectopic pregnancy rate (22%), especially in rudimentary horn

		Data extracted from a single institution, limiting generalizability	Transvaginal ultrasound Renal evaluation (IV pyelogram / renography / ultrasound) Obstetric and reproductive outcome monitoring	pregnancies Intrauterine pregnancy prognosis generally good, though prematurity risk exists Unilateral renal agenesis associated with pregnancy-induced hypertension Removal of rudimentary horn and ipsilateral tube recommended when diagnosed due to risk of rupture and ectopic pregnancy
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DISCUSSION

Overview of main findings

This systematic review of nine studies, which also includes case reports, indicates considerable reproductive and obstructive morbidity. Over nearly all studies, women with this anomaly experience an increased risk of ectopic pregnancies, infertility, early miscarriages, preterm delivery, and foetal malformation, especially within a functional rudimentary horn. Regardless of these risks, pregnancies have more favourable outcomes when earlier diagnosis occurs and is managed carefully.

Reproductive challenges and mechanisms of infertility

Unicornuate uterus is not itself one of the main causes of infertility, but it's one because that may lead to infertility. Other causes include polycystic ovaries, endometriosis, blocking of fallopian tubes and infertility of the male partner. Although the hemi uterus has limitations that lead to subfertility. Abnormal uterine vesiculations, decreased uterus size and myometrial abnormalities have a negative impact on implantation. The miscarriage rate ranges from 32% and 59% as it is high. These findings highlight the infertility nature and early miscarriages in women with a unicornuate uterus.^[4,5,6]

Role and Impact of the Rudimentary Horn

The presence of a rudimentary horn specifically with a functional endometrial cavity was one of the powerful predictors of unavoidable consequences.^[1,2,7,9] Recorded numerous pelvic pain, ectopic pregnancies, endometriosis and horn ruptures. Retrograde menstruation from functional horns comes up with Endometriosis and chronic pelvic Symptoms, evidenced individually by the Case of pulmonary endometriosis.^[1] Ectopic pregnancies implanted in the

horn are transported to life-threatening risk, with ruptures often occurring in the second trimester. Up to 27% of ectopic Pregnancies in large cohorts happen in the rudimentary horn.^[7] These discoveries strongly support prophylactic surgical takeaway of functional horns. To avoid catastrophic outcomes and better reproductive safety.

Pregnancy outcome: Miscarriage, preterm delivery, and live birth

Pregnancy outcome is not good in women with a unicornuate uterus when compared to the general population. Cohort studies reported an increase in the risk of PPRM (Preterm prelabour rupture of membranes), PROM (Premature rupture of membranes), preterm baby, and foetal growth malfunction. This condition, which leads to decreased blood flow to the placenta and overdistension of the uterus, was reported in preterm babies as 21% and 24.5% compared to 7% in controls, and low birth weight was also more prevalent. Regardless of these negative issues, stillbirth rates ranging from 46% to 61% show successful pregnancies due to timely intervention and monitoring.^[3,4,7]

Foetal malpresentation and mode of delivery

Malrepresentation, which is seen in more studies, is reported in 18% and 55% of deliveries. Hemi uterine condition is the cause due to its small size that restricts the movement of the baby, which leads to non-vertex conditions. That's why caesarean-section is generally preferred in some cases. Normal deliveries are also recommended for some selected conditions. Because this c-section is not mandatory in all clinical conditions.^[3,5,6,9]

Twin pregnancies in a unicornuate uterus

Twin babies in this condition are risky. Which leads to abnormalities like PPRM, preterm delivery (85.7%), intrahepatic cholestasis, hypertension, and an increased NICU (Neonatal Intensive Care Unit) admission rate and decreased weight of the baby at the time of birth, so in most of the conditions, a C-section is preferred when compared to normal delivery. This condition finally results in avoiding multiple embryo transfer through IVF (Invitro Fertilization) and improved monitoring in twin pregnancies.^[8]

Gynaecological Morbidity: Endometriosis and Renal Anomalies

Endometriosis was normally related with unicornuate uterus, specifically in women with functional rudimentary horns.^[1,4,7,9] abnormal pelvic anatomy and retrograde menstruation likely provide to this relationship. Renal anomalies, specifically unilateral renal agenesis, were reported in 12–43% of patients.^[5,7,9] This considers the shared Müllerian systems and

embryologic origin of the renal. These results emphasize the need for routine renal imaging and systematic gynaecological assessment in all diagnosed patients.

Diagnostic Accuracy and Importance of Early Identification

Determining the horn communication is used by MRI and 3-dimension ultrasound, emergencies such as horn rupture or advanced ectopic pregnancy is avoided by early diagnosis.^[2,4,9] Precise findings also facilitate pregnancy planning, enhanced pregnancy care, Appropriate surgical remediation.

Comparison With Other Müllerian Anomalies

There are huge similarities in both unicornuate uterus women and didelphic uterus women in reproductive outcome and increased miscarriage, preterm birth, and malpresentation by this both. If unicornuate uterus having rudimentary horn that leads to very serious and risk of ectopic implantation and rupture. This needs more cautious and clinical counselling for unicornuate uterus patients.^[6]

Clinical Implications

Accept simultaneously, the conformation supports classified women with a unicornuate uterus as high-risk obstetric patients. Main clinical advice include: Initial diagnosis using MRI/3D ultrasound.

Prophylactic removal of functional rudimentary horns.

Avoid multiple embryo transfers in IVF.

Comprehensive prenatal surveillance for preterm birth and foetal growth limitation.

Personalised delivery planning derived from presentation and earlier surgical history.

Application of this method can significantly enhance reproductive outcomes and decrease the life-threatening conditions.

Strengths and Limitations of obtainable Literature

Supreme studies were single-centre, retrospective and restricted by small sample sizes. Diversity in diagnostic criteria and incomplete long-term follow-up Further limit applicability. However, the reliability of findings over multiple decades and geographic background support the overall consistency of the literature.

CONCLUSION

Unicornuate uterus describes complex congenital problems with other reproductive problems. These are correlated with increased risks of ectopic pregnancies, miscarriages, preterm delivery, infertility, live birth babies are also achieved with appropriate surgery, early diagnosis and continuous care throughout the gestational period. A multidisciplinary approach from pregnancy confirmation to delivery of the baby is required to regulate both maternal and foetal outcomes.

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